

EARTH SCIENCES

LEGISLATIVE REGULATION OF MINERAL EXTRACTION IN THE USA

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Abstract

This article examines aspects of the legislative regulation of mineral extraction in the USA, aimed at ensuring the sustainable development of the mining industry. The features of the multi-level legal system, encompassing both federal and regional regulation, are highlighted, as they establish a balance between the efficient use of natural resources and adherence to environmental and social standards. Key legislative acts, such as the Clean Air Act, the Clean Water Act, and the Surface Mining Control and Reclamation Act, among others, are analyzed, along with their roles in protecting the environment and workers' health.

Keywords: legal regulation, mineral extraction, USA, environmental protection, sustainable development, mining industry, safety.

Introduction

Mining plays a strategic role in the USA economy, serving as a critical source of natural resources for industry and energy. This sector provides a wide range of natural materials, including metals, minerals, hydrocarbons, and rare earth elements, all essential for manufacturing, construction, and national security. The extraction and processing of these resources require significant effort and technology, while their use is associated with a series of environmental, social, and legal challenges.

Amid growing environmental requirements and the global transition to sustainable energy forms, regulatory oversight of mining activities in the USA has become particularly relevant. The complex system of legal standards and requirements, encompassing both federal and regional legislation, aims to strike a balance between the efficient use of natural resources and the protection of societal interests, the environment, and future generations. This article aims to analyze the existing regulatory framework governing mineral extraction in the USA and to identify contemporary challenges and prospects for its development.

Main part. Historical development of mining legislation

The first legislative acts in the field of mining appeared in the USA in the mid-19th century, during a period of rapid territorial expansion and industrialization. The demand for resources, especially gold and silver, prompted the creation of laws that primarily encouraged resource exploration by offering significant incentives to individuals and companies.

One of the foundational acts was the **General Mining Act** of 1872, which legalized the right of individuals to explore mineral-bearing land on federal properties [1]. This law spurred rapid growth in the mining industry, allowing individual prospectors to extract minerals without substantial obligations to the state.

As industry expanded and energy demands increased in the early 20th century, the USA began to introduce more structured regulations. A significant step was the passage of the **Mineral Leasing Act of 1920**. Unlike the General Mining Act, this legislation estab-

lished a leasing system for coal, oil, and natural gas extraction on federal lands and included rental payments and royalties [2]. This shift marked a departure from unrestricted resource development towards more regulated use, with the federal government acting not only as a regulator but also as a beneficiary of resource revenues.

The second half of the 20th century saw the emergence of large environmental movements and substantial legislative changes. The need to protect the environment and promote sustainable resource use led to the adoption of several laws aimed at reducing the environmental impact of mining activities. In 1969, the **National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA)** was enacted, requiring mining companies to conduct environmental impact assessments before beginning resource development [3]. This law became an important step in forming an environmentally oriented approach to mineral extraction, which gradually extended to other economic sectors.

By the 1970s, the USA had developed a more comprehensive legal framework regulating all aspects of mining. The **Clean Air Act** of 1970 and the **Clean Water Act** of 1972 set strict standards for emissions and wastewater discharges, significantly impacting the mining industry. These acts required companies to implement environmentally safe technologies and to manage their impact on water resources and the atmosphere, making production safer for both the environment and public health.

The historical development of USA mining legislation demonstrates how evolving economic interests and increasing environmental concerns have shaped regulatory frameworks. The modern legislative system, encompassing ownership rights, leasing arrangements, environmental obligations, and payments, differs significantly from the initial approach that promoted unrestricted extraction.

Federal and regional aspects of regulation

Mining regulation in the USA is based on a multi-level system encompassing both federal and regional laws. Federal legislation establishes baseline standards and requirements, which apply primarily to mining activities on public lands. However, regional authorities,

such as state governments and local administrative bodies, have significant freedom to adapt federal regulations to local conditions and may introduce additional requirements to reflect the specifics of their regions [4].

Federal regulations are primarily focused on resources located on public lands. Agencies like the Department of the Interior and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) play key roles in monitoring and regulating mining operations as well as enforcing environmental standards. Federal legislation is geared toward protecting national interests, particularly environmental conservation and the rights of Indigenous peoples residing in areas with active mining operations.

On the other hand, states have the authority to develop their own laws and regulations governing mineral extraction on lands within their jurisdiction. They may also impose stricter requirements than those at the federal level. For example, in oil-producing states like Texas and North Dakota, there are specific rules addressing hydraulic fracturing and methane emission control. In western states such as California and Colorado, where environmental sustainability and water resource protection are especially critical, additional environmental measures are implemented (table 1).

Table 1

Major federal and regional acts regulating mineral extraction in the USA [5]

Regulation level	Key laws and regulatory acts	Goals and key provisions	Examples
Federal	General Mining Act, 1872	Regulates mineral extraction on federal lands.	Applicable to the development of mining claims on federal lands.
	Mineral Leasing Act, 1920s	Leasing system for extracting oil, gas, coal, and certain minerals; includes rental payments and royalties.	Applies to federal land resources.
	Clean Air Act, 1970	Establishes air quality standards, including emission limits for hydrocarbons.	States may impose stricter standards on air quality.
	Clean Water Act, 1972	Regulates discharges into water bodies, protects water resources.	Enforced at the federal level.
Regional (states)	Texas: methane emission regulations	Establishes requirements for methane emission control and hydraulic fracturing operations.	Specific requirements for oil and gas industry.
	California: environmental sustainability	Controls air pollution from mining activities, including methane emissions.	Laws targeted at mitigating climate change impact.
	North Dakota: hydraulic fracturing standards	Sets requirements for hydraulic fracturing operations, including chemical disclosures.	Developed in response to increased shale oil production.
	Colorado: tax on extraction and water resource management	Imposes taxes on resource extraction and allocates part of the revenue to protect local water resources.	Taxes used to mitigate the impact of mining on local communities.

Federal mining legislation establishes basic standards applicable nationwide. However, regional regulations can vary significantly depending on natural conditions, socio-economic priorities, and political preferences. States with stricter environmental requirements impose additional obligations on companies as they aim to minimize the impact of mining on the environment and public health.

Environmental and social standards in legislation

In recent decades, the USA has developed a multi-tiered system of legal oversight [6] that encompasses key aspects of air, water, and land protection, as well as the health and rights of workers.

From an environmental standpoint, one of the first and most significant steps was the introduction of stringent air pollution standards under the **Clean Air Act** of 1970. This law requires companies to control emissions of harmful substances such as sulfur and nitrogen oxides, carbon dioxide, heavy metals, and fine particulate matter, which can be generated during the extraction

and processing of mineral resources. For example, sulfur dioxide emissions must be reduced to no more than 0,12 pounds per million BTU (British Thermal Units) for coal power plants, while nitrogen oxide emissions are limited to 0,07 pounds per million BTU for new energy sources. Exact values may vary depending on the type of facility, construction year, and other factors. Companies exceeding these standards may be fined up to \$25,000 per day for each violation, with fines adjustable for inflation and specific circumstances, as well as variable by category of violation. For mining companies, especially those involved in coal and oil extraction, such standards require significant investments in purification systems and pollution control technology.

The **Clean Water Act** of 1972 regulates discharges into surface and groundwater. This law mandates that mining companies prevent pollutants such as mercury, arsenic, cadmium, and other heavy metals from entering surface and groundwater sources. Violations of these requirements can result in fines and temporary suspension of operations, which could lead to substantial financial losses for large projects.

One of the most important laws aimed at restoring disturbed lands is the **Surface Mining Control and Reclamation Act (SMCRA)** of 1977. This act requires companies to conduct full land reclamation after mining activities, including soil restoration and re-vegetation, to minimize erosion and restore ecosystems. Companies that fail to meet reclamation requirements must pay fines for each affected site, and repeated violations may lead to the revocation of their mining license in the region. This approach encourages more responsible land management and reduces long-term impacts on ecosystems.

Another important legislative element is the **National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA)**, which requires companies to conduct thorough environmental impact assessments before beginning mining at new sites. This process includes a detailed analysis of the potential environmental effects of the project, public

Figure 1. Number of workplace accidents in the USA mining industry [8]

Mining companies are also required to fulfill social obligations to local communities, especially in regions inhabited by Indigenous peoples. These obligations include financial payments in the form of royalties and compensation for land use, as well as ensuring environmental safety for local ecosystems. Violations of Indigenous rights can lead to significant fines and even legal actions, with the possibility of compensation payouts.

The **Payment Transparency Law** (Dodd-Frank Act, Section 1504) mandates that mining companies disclose all payments made to governments in the countries where they operate. Companies are required to report the amounts and purposes of these payments, which helps prevent illicit transactions and enables oversight of revenues and expenditures from resource extraction. Non-compliance with these requirements can result in substantial fines and exclusion from USA stock markets, providing a strong incentive for transparency.

Thus, environmental and social standards in USA legislation play a critical role in managing the mining sector, setting strict requirements and imposing significant penalties for violations. These standards are designed to minimize the environmental impact of mining, protect the health and safety of workers, and ensure the rights of local communities, promoting sustainable development and high social and environmental standards within the industry.

For the USA mining sector to develop sustainably in the future, legislative changes are needed to adapt to new economic and environmental challenges. Potential areas for reform include tightening environmental and safety regulations, increasing royalties and lease fees

discussions, and consultations with local authorities [7]. If a project is found to be environmentally harmful, companies are required to take measures to minimize damage or may even be denied permission to proceed. Failure to comply with this process can result in license renewal denial and fines.

Among social standards, the most important aspects involve worker health and safety requirements established under the **Mine Safety and Health Act of 1977**. This law mandates that companies regularly conduct safety training and equip mines with carbon monoxide and dust monitoring systems to prevent accidents. Failure to meet these requirements can result in fines for each major violation and suspension of activities until full compliance is achieved. Thanks to this law, the number of accidents in the mining sector has significantly decreased (fig. 1).

on federal lands, and introducing additional obligations for land reclamation. Strengthening requirements for rare earth metals extraction is also essential to balance domestic demand for strategically important resources with the need for environmental protection.

In light of these challenges, mining companies are compelled not only to adapt their strategies but also to invest in innovative technologies to minimize environmental damage, ensuring compliance with market demands and regulatory standards.

Conclusion

Mining regulation in the USA provides a multi-tiered framework aimed at protecting the environment, safeguarding worker health and safety, and upholding the rights of local communities. Federal laws establish mandatory baseline standards that must be followed nationwide. States have the authority to adapt and tighten these requirements based on local priorities and natural conditions. This system creates a balance between the efficient use of natural resources and adherence to high standards of environmental and social responsibility, making the mining sector more sustainable and supporting its long-term development.

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